

Strategic development of export–import operations of enterprises in the post–war economic recovery in the context of Ukraine’s integration into the European Union

The subject of the research is the theoretical and practical aspects of the strategic development of export–import operations of enterprises in the post–war economic recovery of Ukraine in the context of its integration into the European Union.

The aim of the research is to determine the strategic directions and prospects for the development of export–import operations of Ukrainian enterprises in the post–war economic recovery in the context of Ukraine’s integration into the European Union.

Research methods. In the course of the study, we used the following general scientific and special methods: literature analysis; statistical analysis; SWOT analysis; comparative analysis; scenario analysis method; expert survey; factor analysis; graphical and tabular analysis and others.

Results of the investigation. It has been established that in the context of Ukraine’s post–war recovery, the strategic development of export–import operations is of particular importance, since economic stability and the reconstruction of the national economy directly depend on Ukraine’s successful integration into the world economic community, in particular into the European Union. The EU is one of Ukraine’s key economic partners, so deepening trade relations and adapting Ukrainian business to European standards is becoming an important task for businesses and the government. It is proved that after the war, Ukraine will need to restore its production potential and infrastructure, which makes the development of foreign economic activity an extremely important factor in stimulating economic growth. It is established that an effective export–import policy will provide enterprises with new opportunities to enter international markets, help attract investment, increase the competitiveness of Ukrainian goods and services, and create new jobs. In addition, Ukraine’s integration into the EU implies active adaptation of legislation, economic instruments and standards to European norms, which will require flexibility and readiness for reforms from enterprises. The author analyzes and finds out that an important component is also the prospects for expanding trade with the EU countries through the Free Trade Area, which is already operating under the EU–Ukraine Association Agreement, which contributes to improving the quality of Ukrainian products, developing small and medium–sized enterprises and diversifying export markets. It is proved that the identification of strategic directions for the development of export–import operations in the post–war period is extremely relevant, which will ensure Ukraine’s economic recovery and its successful integration into the European and world markets.

Scope of the results. Strategic development management, foreign economic activity, export–import operations, integration into the EU, business economics, international economics.

Conclusions. The study has determined that export–import operations play a key role in the recovery of Ukraine’s post–war economy and integration into the European Union. Despite the numerous obstacles faced by Ukrainian enterprises as a result of the war, the strategic development of this sector opens up new opportunities for economic growth. The author proposes the main strategic directions for the development of export–import operations for Ukrainian enterprises, namely: integration into the EU and adaptation to the requirements of European markets; diversification of export markets; modernization and digitalization of processes; and stimulation of state export support programs. Thus, integration into the EU, modernization of production processes, diversification of export markets, and development of state programs to support exporters will allow Ukraine to take its rightful place on the world economic stage and ensure stable economic growth in the future.

Keywords: export–import operations, strategic development, post–war recovery, national economy, integration, European Union, competitiveness.

Стратегічний розвиток експортно–імпортних операцій підприємств в післявоєнному відновленні економіки в контексті інтеграції України до Європейського Союзу

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні та практичні аспекти стратегічного розвитку експортно–імпортних операцій підприємств в післявоєнному відновленні економіки України в контексті її інтеграції до Європейського Союзу.

Метою дослідження є визначення стратегічних напрямів та перспектив розвитку експортно–імпортних операцій українських підприємств в післявоєнному відновленні економіки в контексті інтеграції України до Європейського Союзу.

Методи дослідження. В процесі дослідження нами було використано такі загальнонаукові та спеціальні методи: аналіз літератури; статистичний аналіз; SWOT–аналіз; порівняльний аналіз; метод сценарного аналізу; експертне опитування; факторний аналіз; графічно–табличний та інші.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що в умовах післявоєнного відновлення України стратегічний розвиток експортно–імпортних операцій набуває особливої ваги, оскільки економічна стабільність і відбудова національної економіки безпосередньо залежать від успішної інтеграції України у світову економічну спільноту, зокрема у Європейський Союз. ЄС є одним із ключових економічних партнерів України, тому поглиблення торговельних відносин і адаптація українського бізнесу до європейських стандартів стає важливим завданням для підприємств та уряду. Доведено, що після війни перед Україною постане потреба відновлення виробничого потенціалу та інфраструктури, що робить розвиток зовнішньоекономічної діяльності надзвичайно важливим чинником стимулювання економічного зростання. Встановлено, що ефективна експортно–імпортна політика забезпечить підприємствам нові можливості для виходу на міжнародні ринки, сприятиме залученню інвестицій, підвищенню конкурентоспроможності українських товарів і послуг та створенню нових робочих місць. Крім того, інтеграція України в ЄС передбачає активну адаптацію законодавства, економічних інструментів і стандартів до європейських норм, що вимагатиме від підприємств гнучкості та готовності до реформ. Проаналізовано та з'ясовано, що важливою складовою є також перспективи розширення торгівлі з країнами ЄС за рахунок Зони вільної торгівлі, яка вже функціонує в рамках Угоди про асоціацію між Україною та ЄС, що сприяє підвищенню якості української продукції, розвитку малих і середніх підприємств та диверсифікації експортних ринків. Доведено, що визначення стратегічних напрямів розвитку експортно–імпортних операцій в післявоєнний період є надзвичайно актуальним, що дозволить забезпечити економічне відновлення України та її успішну інтеграцію в європейський і світовий ринки.

Галузь застосування результатів. Управління стратегічним розвитком, зовнішньоекономічна діяльність, експортно–імпортні операції, інтеграція до ЄС, економіка підприємства, міжнародна економіка.

Висновки. В результаті дослідження було визначено, що експортно–імпортні операції відіграють ключову роль у відновленні післявоєнної економіки України та інтеграції до Європейського Союзу. Незважаючи на численні перешкоди, що постали перед українськими підприємствами внаслідок війни, стратегічний розвиток експортно–імпортних операцій відкриває нові можливості для економічного зростання. Запропоновано основні стратегічні напрями розвитку експортно–імпортних операцій для українських підприємств, а саме: інтеграція в ЄС та адаптація до вимог європейських ринків; диверсифікація експортних ринків; модернізація та цифровізація процесів; стимулювання державних програм підтримки експорту. Отже, інтеграція до ЄС, модернізація виробничих процесів, диверсифікація експортних ринків і розвиток державних програм підтримки експортерів дозволять Україні посісти гідне місце на світовій економічній арені та забезпечити стабільне економічне зростання в майбутньому.

Ключові слова: експортно–імпортні операції, стратегічний розвиток, післявоєнне відновлення, економіка країни, інтеграція, Європейський Союз, конкурентоспроможність.

Formulation of the problem. In the context of Ukraine's post-war recovery, the issue of strategic development of export-import operations is of particular importance, as economic stability and the reconstruction of the national economy directly depend on Ukraine's successful integration into the global economic system, in particular the European Union. The EU is one of Ukraine's key economic partners, so deepening trade relations and adapting Ukrainian businesses to European standards is becoming an important task for businesses and the government. After the war, Ukraine will need to rebuild its production capacity and infrastructure, which makes the development of foreign economic activity an extremely important factor in stimulating economic growth. A successful export-import policy will provide businesses with new opportunities to enter international markets, help attract investment, increase the competitiveness of Ukrainian goods and services, and create new jobs. In addition, Ukraine's integration into the EU requires active adaptation of legislation, economic instruments, and standards to European norms, which will require companies to be flexible and ready for reforms. Changes in trade, logistics, customs clearance and other key aspects of export and import operations require a strategic approach to planning and development. An important component is also the prospect of expanding trade with the EU through the Free Trade Area, which is already operating under the EU-Ukraine Association Agreement, which contributes to improving the quality of Ukrainian products, developing small and medium-sized enterprises, and diversifying export markets. Thus, studying the current state and identifying strategic directions for the development of export-import operations in the post-war period is extremely relevant and will ensure Ukraine's economic recovery and its successful integration into the European and global markets.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The research on strategic directions for the development of export-import operations of enterprises in the postwar period of the national economy in the context of Ukraine's integration into the EU is quite new and important for Ukraine due to its aspirations for integration into the EU and the challenges that arise in the context of postwar reconstruction. Nevertheless, there are several Ukrainian and foreign authors who study related topics, includ-

ing economic integration, international trade development, and export-import operations. Among domestic scholars: O. Paskhaver, an economist who studies Ukraine's economic policy, development strategy in the context of European integration and post-conflict recovery; A. Galchynskiy, who studies macroeconomics, Ukraine's integration processes with the EU, and economic policy during the transformation period; I. Alekseenko, whose research is devoted to international trade and enterprise strategies in the context of globalization and Ukraine's integration into the EU; O. Bilorus, who studies Ukraine's integration into the global and European economy; and T. Kozlov, who studies Ukraine's integration into the global and European economy.

Among foreign authors-scientists, this issue is dealt with by: D. Rodrik, an American economist who studies globalization, international trade and economic policy for developing countries; J. Tirole, a French economist known for his work on market structure, in particular, competition in global markets; P. Krugman, who specializes in international trade and economic policy, especially in the context of integration processes and trade blocs such as the EU; S. Johnson, a British-American economist who studies economic crises, their impact on international trade and economic policy Baldwin, who studies globalization, economic integration, and trade policy, in particular, economic growth and global trade flows. However, for an in-depth analysis of the strategic development of export-import operations in the context of Ukraine's integration into the EU, we consider it necessary to study the issue of Ukraine's economic recovery after the end of the war, and to propose the main strategic directions of export-import operations with a focus on Ukraine's integration into the EU.

Presenting main material. Ukraine is facing a difficult economic situation as a result of the war that began in 2022. The armed conflict has significantly weakened the national economy, destroyed infrastructure, and worsened the business environment. However, in the post-war period, Ukraine should focus on recovery, strengthening international relations, and gradual integration into the European Union (EU). One of the key areas of this process is the development of export-import operations that contribute to economic recovery, increase foreign exchange earnings, and integration into global markets [1; 5; 7; 8; 12; 16; 19; 20].

Table 1. Ukraine’s foreign trade balance in 2019–2023 (UAH million)

Years	Nominal GDP	Exports	Imports	Balance
2019	3974564	1636416	-1947599	-311183
2020	4194102	1637399	-1681526	-44127
2021	5459574	2224704	-2286067	-61363
2022	5191028	1840563	-2712325	-871762
2023	6537825	1868904	-3237014	-1368110

At the beginning of the war, Ukraine’s exports and imports declined significantly due to damage to the transportation infrastructure, loss of access to seaports, and reduced production capacity of enterprises in the frontline regions. In 2022–2023, the country’s economy lost a significant portion of its exports due to the blockade of the Black Sea, the main channel for exporting agricultural products and metallurgical products. However, after the conclusion of international agreements and the opening of alternative transportation corridors, the situation began to gradually improve (Table 1).

It can be clearly seen that, along with the growth in export and import operations, imports to Ukraine have been chronically outpacing exports in recent years, with the difference sometimes reaching 8% of GDP. Thus, the negative balance of Ukraine’s foreign trade in goods in January–April 2023 increased almost 40 times compared to the same period in 2022. In the first quarter of 2024, the deficit increased to \$7 billion. In the first quarter of 2014, the deficit increased to \$7 billion. Exports of goods from Ukraine decreased by almost 20% to USD 13.5 billion, while imports increased by 22% to USD 20.5 billion. In January–April 2023, the export–import coverage ratio amounted to 0.65 (0.99 in January–April 2002).

Thus, the main obstacles to export–import operations in the postwar period will be:

- logistical problems – the post-war restoration of the transport infrastructure is one of the biggest problems for the development of international trade. Many transportation routes have been destroyed or need serious reconstruction. It is also important to develop new routes across the western borders to reduce dependence on Black Sea ports;
- reduced production capacity – The war in Ukraine has led to a decline in industrial production, especially in metallurgy and chemicals, which were the mainstays of Ukrainian exports. Some enterprises were damaged or destroyed, and their recovery will require significant investments;

- rising import costs – as a result of the economic crisis and inflation, the cost of importing energy, raw materials and technology has increased significantly, which affects the cost of Ukrainian goods;

- decrease in the purchasing power of the population – due to the war and economic instability, the level of citizens’ income has decreased, which has affected the domestic market and reduced the demand for imported goods [2; 4; 9; 11; 15; 18; 21].

In order to improve the economic situation and ensure successful further integration into the EU, we propose the following strategic directions for the development of export–import operations for Ukrainian enterprises (Fig. 1) [3; 6; 10; 13; 17; 22]:

1. Integration into the EU and adaptation to the requirements of European markets. Given the conclusion of the Association Agreement with the EU, Ukrainian companies need to adapt their products to European standards and requirements, which includes not only technical standards but also product safety and quality, environmental and energy saving requirements. Deeper cooperation with the EU will allow Ukrainian companies to gain access to the single European market, which will be a significant factor in increasing exports. The importance of integration into the EU is due to the following factors (Table 2) [11; 14; 18; 20; 23]:

2. Diversification of export markets. Besides the EU, the Middle East, Asia, and Africa may become the main export destinations. The post-war period opens up new opportunities for developing trade with countries that are looking for new suppliers of agricultural products, metallurgy, chemicals, and pharmaceuticals. The importance of diversifying export markets is due to the following factors:

- reducing the risks of economic dependence – market diversification avoids excessive dependence on individual countries and reduces the risks associated with fluctuations in these markets;

- increase in competitiveness – working in different markets helps companies adapt to different requirements and standards, which improves their

Fig. 1. Strategic development of export-import operations of enterprises in the post-war recovery in the context of EU integration

competitiveness and gives them a competitive advantage both in the domestic and foreign markets;

- expanding the potential for economic growth – diversification of export markets opens up new opportunities for revenue growth, which helps to attract foreign investment, create new jobs and develop technologies;

- resilience to geopolitical changes – market diversification is especially important in times of geopolitical instability. Having an aggressor neighbor, Ukraine is interested in reducing its dependence on the markets of countries with which it may have political or military conflicts. Focusing on

the markets of the EU, Asia, Africa and other regions makes exports less vulnerable to external political factors;

- integration into global supply chains – in the process of diversifying export markets, enterprises become part of global supply chains, which facilitates access to new technologies, better resources and more favorable conditions for production and creates opportunities for cooperation with large multinational corporations and international organizations;

- taking advantage of international trade agreements – diversification allows to fully utilize the benefits of international agreements, such as the

Table 2. Importance and adaptation to Ukraine's integration into the EU

Factor	Characteristics
Access to the large and stable EU market	The EU is one of the largest economic blocs in the world with a high level of purchasing power. Integration into the EU will provide Ukrainian enterprises with access to this market of approximately 450 million consumers, which will help expand the geography of sales and stimulate export growth.
Free trade area	Ukraine already has an Association Agreement with the EU, which includes a DCFTA, allowing Ukrainian companies to export products to Europe at reduced tariffs or without any customs restrictions, which significantly increases the economic attractiveness of the European market.
Improvement of product competitiveness and quality	European markets have strict requirements for product quality, safety standards, environmental and social standards. Adaptation of Ukrainian enterprises to these requirements will stimulate modernization of production, introduction of international quality standards and improvement of technologies, which will not only help enterprises to be competitive in the EU, but also increase their ability to compete in other global markets.
Diversification of export and import flows	Integration into the EU will help Ukrainian enterprises to reduce dependence on certain markets, in particular the CIS and Russia, which will reduce risks from potential economic or political restrictions on other markets, strengthening the resilience of Ukraine's economy to external shocks.
Attracting foreign investment	Deeper economic integration with the EU could attract more foreign investors as the country becomes more stable and predictable in terms of legal and economic policies. EU investors may be more interested in investing in Ukrainian companies if they comply with European standards and regulations.
Protection of intellectual property	The EU pays great attention to intellectual property issues, which is important for high-tech industries. Ukrainian companies will need to adapt to these rules, which will help protect their own innovations and at the same time facilitate access to innovative solutions from the EU.
Development of infrastructure and logistics	To effectively conduct export-import operations with the EU, it is necessary to develop infrastructure, especially logistics chains that will ensure timely delivery of goods, including modernization of transport routes, customs procedures, and digitalization of trade processes.
Support for small and medium-sized businesses	Adapting to European standards opens up new opportunities for Ukrainian SMEs, as the EU provides various financial support, lending, and advisory programs that can stimulate the creation of new export businesses and promote a competitive environment.

EU-Ukraine Association Agreement, which provides for easier access to the European market, lower customs barriers and harmonization of legislation. In addition, Ukraine can develop relations with other countries outside the EU by concluding bilateral free trade agreements;

- flexibility in response to changes in demand – diversified export markets allow for rapid reorientation of exports depending on changes in demand, which minimizes losses in the event of a decline in demand in one of the markets;

- support for economic stability and sustainable development – for Ukraine, market diversification will contribute to economic stability and export flow development, which is important for sustainable economic development [15; 17; 19; 23; 24].

3. Modernization and digitalization of processes. Modernization and digitalization of processes as a strategic direction for the development of export-

import operations is a key element for the successful integration of national economies into global markets, especially in the context of Ukraine's post-war recovery and integration into the European Union. This direction has a number of critical advantages that contribute to the competitiveness of enterprises and overall economic stability (Table 3) [4; 6; 11; 23]:

4. Stimulate government export support programs. In order to stimulate exports, it is necessary to develop government programs to support Ukrainian exporters, including financial assistance, reduction of export tariffs, information support, and easier access to international markets. In addition, it is important to ensure that conditions are created to attract foreign investors to restore the industrial sector and modernize production. For Ukraine in the post-war period and in the context of its integration into the EU, this issue is becoming

Table 3. Modernization and digitalization of processes as a strategic direction for the development of export–import operations

Benefits	Importance in increasing competitiveness
Increased efficiency of operations	Modernization of logistics and production processes allows companies to carry out export and import operations faster and more efficiently. The introduction of digital technologies helps to automate processes, reduce operating costs and improve the accuracy of supply chain management.
Reduced bureaucracy and reduced time to complete procedures	The digitalization of customs procedures and the use of electronic documents significantly speeds up the passage of goods across the border, which reduces administrative barriers. Electronic platforms such as eCustoms or the Single Window can provide automated processing of customs declarations and permits.
Improved access to new markets	Digital platforms for international trade, such as marketplaces, electronic exchanges, or export management systems, enable businesses to quickly find new customers and partners internationally, allowing Ukrainian enterprises to actively integrate into global value chains and increase exports to the EU and other regions of the world.
Increased transparency and security	Digitalization provides a higher level of transparency at every stage of export and import operations. The use of technologies such as blockchain can guarantee data accuracy, prevent fraud, and promote trust between market participants. Implementation of modern cybersecurity systems allows protecting enterprise information systems from external threats, which is critical in the current international trade environment.
Adaptation to EU standards	Ukraine’s integration into the EU requires harmonization of regulatory and technical standards governing export and import operations.
Increasing resilience to global challenges	The use of digital technologies will help businesses implement and comply with quality, environmental, and safety requirements, which is essential for entering EU markets.
Attracting investments	Digital solutions allow businesses to be more flexible and adaptive to changes in the global environment. Digitalization also helps businesses recover faster from crises or conflicts, ensuring business resilience in an uncertain environment.

particularly relevant. Below are the main aspects of the importance of such programs:

- strengthening the economy and GDP growth – Exports are one of the most important drivers of economic growth, where export promotion helps to increase sales of Ukrainian goods and services in foreign markets, leading to higher revenues for enterprises and, consequently, higher GDP. Government export support programs can provide companies with additional resources and tools to develop new markets, such as the EU market;
- diversification of sales markets – state support programs help Ukrainian enterprises diversify their export markets, reducing dependence on individual countries or regions, which is especially important in the context of EU integration, where there is a wide range of opportunities for Ukrainian producers;
- competitiveness in international markets – government programs can help enterprises improve their competitiveness by providing financial assistance, expert support, and training. Important programs include support for innovation, modernization of production, and certification of goods in accordance with international standards, espe-

cially European ones, which opens doors to new markets and increases the chances of success in competition with international companies;

- increase investment attractiveness – export-oriented government programs can create a favorable environment for attracting foreign investors. Investors often prefer countries with developed export sectors, as this indicates economic stability, a high level of international integration, and potential for growth. Integration into the EU enables Ukrainian companies to attract new capital, which has a positive impact on the overall development of the economy;
- increase in employment – the development of the export sector, stimulated by government programs, contributes to the creation of new jobs. Higher production for foreign markets requires additional labor resources. Thus, export promotion has a positive impact on the labor market and helps to reduce unemployment, which is especially important in the post-war period;
- improving infrastructure and logistics – government export support programs often include the development of infrastructure necessary

for efficient trade, including modernization of the transport system, improvement of customs procedures, and creation of new logistics centers. In post-war Ukraine, this is of critical importance, as rebuilding infrastructure is a key element in stimulating exports and imports;

- improving national security – a strong export sector can help stabilize the national economy, which in turn increases the level of economic security of the country. Strengthening Ukraine's position in international markets reduces dependence on foreign resources and contributes to resilience to external shocks, such as political or economic sanctions;

- adaptation to EU market requirements – integration into the EU requires Ukraine to comply with many EU norms and standards. Government programs can help Ukrainian enterprises with this adaptation through consultations, trainings, and information on necessary changes in production, logistics, and product certification [3; 6; 8; 13; 17; 22].

Thus, only by overcoming the post-war challenges will Ukrainian enterprises be able to increase the efficiency of export and import activities and accelerate integration into the EU. The advantages of Ukraine's integration into the EU in this context are:

1. Trade preferences in the EU. One of the key advantages of Ukraine's integration into the EU is access to the European market with duty-free or reduced tariffs.

2. Restoration of infrastructure. Restoring infrastructure is a priority for export and import development. Railroads, roads, airports, ports – all of these require large-scale investment and close cooperation with international partners, including the EU, to ensure the smooth flow of goods and services.

3. Cooperation with foreign investors. Ukraine's integration into European economic and trade structures requires the attraction of foreign investors who can help modernize enterprises and create new production facilities. European investors can become important partners in Ukraine's post-war recovery, especially in the areas of high technology, energy, agriculture, and green energy [17; 19; 21; 22; 23; 24].

Conclusions

Export–import operations play a key role in the recovery of Ukraine's post-war economy and integration into the European Union. Despite the numerous obstacles faced by Ukrainian enterprises as a result of the war, the strategic development

of this sector opens up new opportunities for economic growth. The main strategic directions for the development of export–import operations for Ukrainian enterprises are proposed, namely:

- Integration into the EU and adaptation to the requirements of European markets (access to the large and stable EU market; free trade zone; improvement of product competitiveness and quality; diversification of export and import flows; attraction of foreign investments; protection of intellectual property; development of infrastructure and logistics; support small and medium business).

- Diversification of export markets (reducing the risks of economic dependence; increasing competitiveness; expanding the potential for economic growth; resistance to geopolitical changes; integration into global supply chains; taking advantage of international trade agreements; flexibility in response to changes in demand; maintaining economic stability and sustainable development).

- Modernization and digitalization of processes (increasing the efficiency of operations; reducing bureaucracy and shortening the time for procedures; improving access to new markets; increasing transparency and security; adapting to EU standards; increasing resistance to global challenges; attracting investments).
- 4. Stimulation of state export support programs (strengthening of the economy and growth; diversification of sales markets; competitiveness on international markets; increasing investment attractiveness; increasing employment; improving infrastructure and logistics; increasing the level of national security; adapting to the requirements of the EU market).

Therefore, integration with the EU, modernization of production processes, diversification of export markets and the development of state programs to support exporters will allow Ukraine to take a worthy place on the world economic stage and ensure stable economic growth in the future.

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КРУПСЬКИЙ В. С.

Стимулювання сільськогосподарської переробки

Предметом дослідження є стимулювання сільськогосподарської переробки.

Метою дослідження є визначити найбільш ефективні шляхи стимулювання сільськогосподарської переробки.

Методи дослідження. У статті використані діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, метод аналізу і синтезу, порівняльний метод, метод узагальнення даних.

Результати роботи. У статті проаналізовані основні аспекти сільськогосподарської переробки. Визначено і охарактеризовано найбільш ефективні шляхи стимулювання сільськогосподарської переробки. Визначена необхідність встановлення синергії між державними структурами, бізнесом та громадськістю.

Висновки. Сільське господарство є важливою складовою економіки багатьох країн, і його переробка відіграє важливу роль у забезпеченні продовольчої безпеки та створенні доданої вартості. Для стимулювання сільськогосподарської переробки необхідно запровадити комплексний підхід, це інвестування у сучасні технології, навчання кадрів та розширення інфраструктури. По-перше, впровадження інноваційних технологій дасть можливість зменшити витрати на виробництво та покращити якість продукції. Для цього необхідно співпрацювати з науковими установами та приймати оптимальні рішення для кожного виду переробки. По-друге, навчання та підвищення кваліфікації працівників є невід'ємною складовою успішного розвитку галузі. Організація семінарів та тренінгів сприятиме впровадженню нових методів роботи та підвищенню продуктивності. Розбудова інфраструктури, включаючи холодительно-транспортні системи та підприємства з переробки, створить необхідні умови для росту виробництва. Інвестування у ці сфери підвищить конкурентоспроможність та сприятиме економічному розвитку регіонів.

Ключові слова: кластери, маркетинг, товар, агропереробка, фінансування, інфраструктура, екологія, ринок, сільське господарство, інвестиції.

KRUPSKYI V. S.

Stimulation of agricultural processing

The subject of the study is stimulation of agricultural processing.

The purpose of the study is to determine the most effective ways of stimulating agricultural processing.

Research methods. The article uses the dialectical method of scientific knowledge, the method of analysis and synthesis, the comparative method, and the method of summarizing data.

Work results. The article analyzes the main aspects of agricultural processing. The most effective ways of stimulating agricultural processing have been identified and characterized. The need to establish synergy between state structures, business and the public has been identified.